

EFFECT OF REFLECTIVE LANGUAGE ACQUISITION MODEL (RLAM) ON SPEAKING SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The influence in English language has been more prominent in all spheres of modern world, such as education, trade, administration, migration and others. The various boards of education instituted several measures for improving communication skills in English in India, it seems that the objectives of English education could not satisfy the basic interpersonal communication skills of the students in state schools. In this context, the researcher developed a new model based on reflective practices to meet the goals of English language acquisition titled as Reflective Language Acquisition Model (RLAM). The present study aimed at testing the effect of the RLAM for developing Speaking Skills among secondary school students. Results reveal that there is a significant progress after the treatment of RLAM, particularly speaking ability of secondary school students.

Key words: *Reflective Language Acquisition Model (RLAM), Speaking skills, Secondary school students*

1. Introduction

Language education has been instrumental in the overall progress of any nation. During the unification of India, the diversity of languages was a great hindrance among the people of India. Being India a multilingual country, it executed the official languages act in 1963 and considered English as an associate official language of India. Later three language formula was implemented in Indian states. Over a period of 50 years, the importance of English education has been increasing day by day. It contributed a lot for the growth and development of the nation. English makes it easy to link the people within the states of the country and with the people of other nations as it is a global language. Now in India, English has been considered as a second language in educational purpose and it aims at developing the communication skills of a learner especially the fundamental skills namely, listening, speaking, reading and writing.

The influence in English language has been more prominent in all spheres of modern world, such as education, trade, administration, migration and others. The three-language formula for learning language was formulated in the year 1968 by the Government of India, has crossed 50 years. Yet several policies on education, curriculum frameworks have been implemented by Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) and other bodies, the schools of country could not fulfil the goals of English language Education. Within the eight years of education constitutionally guaranteed to every child, it should be possible to achieve Basic English language proficiency in a span of about four years. (NCF 2005). Acquisition of Basic English language skills is still a distant dream of the vast majority of school going children in India. It also needs to be recognised that there is a growing demand for learning English language among all sections of people ([National Policy on Education 2016](#)).

Although the various commissions and boards of education instituted several measures for improving communication skills in English, it seems that the objectives of English education could not satisfy the basic interpersonal communication skills of the students in state schools. The existing practices in second language education do not bear the fruits of language education in most of the cases. The quality of second language in government and government aided institutions is not up to the expected standards, and the methodology of teaching is also traditional in nature. Even after ten or fifteen years of schooling or college education most of the students are not able to communicate in English confidently. It seems that the present practices are not practical and sufficient to make them better communicators. In this context, it is needed to find alternate ways for improving pedagogical practice which is very essential for overcoming the drawbacks of quality language education for the creation of sound learning practices in school system.

In the case of language education reflective pedagogy can do a lot in revamping the existing learning situations. Thus, reflective practices can become a practical approach for finding out the reasons of failures and to make the required changes, thereto for transforming the learners as successful communicators. Pragmatically, the students are unable to write and speak accurately and proficiently by the intended instructional programme. In order to improve the existing system, an alternative instructional design is essential for effective curriculum transaction. The present study aimed to develop an instructional pedagogy in the form of reflective language acquisition model, for enriching Speaking skills in English among the secondary school students of Kerala State. This experimental study also finds out the effectiveness of RLAM in making the language learning process more meaningful and quite interesting.

2. Theoretical underpinnings

Reflective Practice is “the capacity to reflect on action so as to engage in a process of continuous learning”, which, according to the originator of the term, is “one of the defining characteristics of professional practice” (Schon, 1983). Reflection has been very prevalent in all sectors of teacher education, including vocational and adult education, for a number of years. Despite numerous articles, there is little solid empirical evidence that supports the view that it results in superior teaching practices in language education. To move from the older teaching model to the newer one, language teachers need to think about what they do and how and why they do it. Reflective learning is the process of examining and exploring an experience which creates and clarifies meaning which results a different conceptual perspective (Boyd & Fales, 1983). This becomes the central to understanding the experiential learning process. It is a way of allowing students to go back from their respective learning experience to help them to develop critical thinking skills and improve their future performance by analysing their own experience. Reflective Teaching is an inquiry approach that emphasises an ethic of caring, a constructivist approach to teaching, and creative problem solving (Henderson, 1996). Reflection or “critical reflection” refers to an activity or process in which an experience is recalled, considered, and evaluated, usually in relation to a broader purpose. It is a response to past experience and involves conscious recall and examination of the experience as a basis for evaluation and decision-making and as a source for planning and action (Richards & Nunan, 1990). The main value of reflective teaching lies in its potential to clarify thinking (Bailey et al., 1996). Reflective teaching has been interpreted as the process of examining how teachers learn to teach, existing research on teacher cognitions, teachers' knowledge, and the context of teachers' learning has potential to extend our understanding of the role of reflection in teacher education (Calderhead, 1989). It becomes a self-assessment of teaching in which the teacher analyses pedagogy, expresses reasons and strengths of strategies and identifies the areas for revision or improvement.

2500 years back, Greeks used to practice reflection in the form of contemplation in search of truth. There are certain references from Confucius (551-479BC) (Confucius, *The Analects*: ch2, compiled posthumously) the Chinese philosopher who used to apply reflective learning. A Swiss psychologist, Jean Piaget proposed a theory based on the stages of development. He stressed that experience, concept, reflection and action are the foundations by which adult thought is developed (Piaget, 1961). It means reflection is essential for learning which links reflection with action, to support critically reflective thinking for new understanding and knowledge.

Wolfgang Kohler conducted several studies using animals. He used the term ‘insight learning’ (Kohler, 1967). Based on the experiments he saw insight as a thought process leading to alternative action. An American Professor, Donald Schon produced a series of books on learning as reflective practice. He (Schon, 1987) emphasised on reflective practitioner and professional reflective practice. Gibbs, in his cycle there are six elements (Gibbs, 1988) which encourage the use of critical reflection and it converts new learning and knowledge into action and change. John Dewey an American philosopher is known as the founder of Experiential education. He tried to link reflection and action, to enable new experience and knowledge.

Barbara Larivee gives us an opportunity to look back at what happened in a more measured and objective way (Larivee, 2000). An American sociologist of Columbia University, Jack Mezirow suggests that self-reflection can empower us to be more open and emotionally capable of changing and reflecting. This is a liberating process of intellectual and emotional growth (Mezirow, 2000). Jenny Moon (J. A. Moon, 2013) defines reflection as a mental process of thinking about what we have done, learned or experienced. American educationalist, David Kolb proposed experiential learning theory (Kolb, 2014). His diagram consists of four main stages of the learning process as a continuous loop. It involves experience, reflection, learning and experimentation. An English educationalist, Stephen Brookfield, proposed ‘lens’ theory (Brookfield, 2017), which suggests reflection on our work or practice through other lenses from multiple perspectives.

3. Construction of RLAM

The RLAM developed for the study is based on theories and models namely, Graham Gibbs’ model of reflection (1988), Chris Johns’ Model of Reflection (1994), Atkins and Murphys’ Model of Reflection (1993) and Kolbs’ Experiential Learning Cycle (1984). These concepts and theories were transformed into four phases. The researcher developed the instructional material based on the theoretical basis of Reflective Teaching and Learning. The researcher went through more than a dozen models which were related to reflective practices and carefully analysed the various phases. The core components for testing Speaking Skills were fixed as Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation/Coherence and cohesion, Vocabulary and Language control.

Analysing the conditions and requirements of government funded schools, the researcher prepared the instructional design Reflective Language Acquisition Model (RLAM) based on the theoretical as well as the linguistic principles of language learning.

The following table shows a brief description of the four phases of RLAM.

Table 1

Phases of RLAM

Phase No.	Name of the Phase	Teacher & Student Activity
Phase I	Experiencing Content	The teacher provides an exposure to the language by communicating the text material; learners listen attentively
Phase II	Imitating for Acquisition	The interaction between the teacher and the taught takes place (Speaking)
Phase III	Reflecting the Learning Process	Reflection in-action about the communicated topic takes place (individual & group)
Phase IV	Analysing the Learning Strategy	The learner writes reflective diary on what they learnt newly

Lesson transcripts prepared for the treatment can be used for teaching English among secondary school students. Corrections involved in the model will provide strong conviction about linguistic elements of English. The linguistic principles incorporated into the model provide a sense of direction towards teaching and learning English.

4. Hypothesis Development and RLAM testing

Reflective teaching and learning means looking at what we do in the classroom, thinking about why we do it, and thinking about if it works - a process of self - observation and self -evaluation. Analysing and evaluating the information about what goes on in class room, we identify and explore own experiences and practices. This may lead to changes and improvements in teaching-learning process. In fact, the development of reflective practices is the integration of theory and practice, the cyclic pattern of experience and the conscious application of that learning experience. Reflective Practices can be seen and has been recognised in many teaching and learning scenarios (Wopereis, et

al, 2010). In education, reflective practices refer to the process of the educator studying his or her own teaching methods and determining what works best for the students. It involves the consideration of the ethical consequences of classroom procedures on students (Larrivee, 2000). In the same way, reflective learning practice refers to the process of the learner studying his own methods for better learning. Systematic reflection makes efficient use of time, money and energy in providing practitioners immediate feedback on teaching performance which focuses or refocuses on insights into teaching. Reflection is helpful for the enrichment of professional as well as personal improvement. The application of the RLAM model would encourage learners as well as the teachers of teaching English at primary, secondary and tertiary levels in adopting reflective practices for their day - to - day teaching situations. Regular application of RLAM will make the students confident speakers of English. It focuses on Speaking Skills as these are primary in learning a language. The model will create rich learning situations for the acquisition of language skills. The instructional design is highly flexible and has the potential to change the way the students communicate in individual and group learning situations.

The major objective of the present study was to compare the effectiveness of RLAM with the Activity Oriented Method (AOM) of teaching English among secondary school students of Kerala State. The study hypothesises that the RLAM developed will enable the teacher of English to help the learners an exposure to the English language through reflective practices. A teacher with sufficient language skills by using RLAM can definitely help every learner to acquire mastery over the four fundamental skills in English. The following hypotheses were developed and tested for the purpose for the study.

The students taught through Reflective Language Acquisition Model (Experimental group) have significantly higher gain scores in Speaking skills than those taught through the existing Activity Oriented Method (Control group).

The developed Reflective Language Acquisition Model is more effective in enhancing Speaking skills in English than the existing Activity Oriented Method among Secondary School Students.

5. Method

5.1. The Research Design

The present study aims to compare the effectiveness of RLAM with the Activity Oriented Method (AOM) of teaching English among secondary school students of Kerala State. Therefore, the researcher opted Experimental Method for the present study. In experimental research, researchers manipulate an independent variable with treatment and compare the conditions exercising high degree of controlling and is a logical method of testing hypotheses by random assignment and replication. It helps to find out whether the new method of teaching is more effective than the method prevalent in attaining the set objectives.

In the present study, the researcher applied Pre-test - Post-test Cross Over Non-equivalent Groups Design, a longitudinal study, in which each group of experiment received a sequence of treatments, in other words it took repeated measures. The study consisted of two experimental and two control groups. In this experimental research design, the equivalence of the experimental and control group is established by randomisation of subjects to the experimental and control groups. Hence the researcher decided to conduct the experimental study in two intact non-equated groups and statistically equated the groups by controlling the effect of the - scores as covariates. Therefore, the design selected for the present study was Pre-test – Post-test Cross Over Non-equivalent Groups Design. In order to solve the problem of non-equivalent group, the researcher applied ANCOVA.

5.2. Variables of the Study

In order to fulfil the objectives of the present study, the investigator selected the following independent and dependent variables.

Independent variable

Independent variable in the study was treatment variable which has two levels.

- Instruction in English using RLAM
- Instruction in English using AOM - existing in the secondary schools which follow state curriculum.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable of the study is Speaking Skills and its components, which are Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation/Coherence and cohesion, Vocabulary and Language control.

5.3. Data Collection and Sample

The researcher identified two intact divisions of students of standard Nine from a Higher Secondary School, in Kottayam District of Kerala State and randomly assigned a group as experimental and the other as control group. The experimental group consisted of 37 students and the control group consisted of 38 students. During phase I Experimentation, the experimental group was taught using RLAM and the control group was taught using AOM. In phase II Experimentation, Control group became the experimental group and the experimental group became control group. A diagrammatic representation of the experimentations in the two phases is presented below.

Phase I Experimentation

Fig. 1. Phase I Experimentation

Phase II Experimentation

Fig. 2. Phase II Experimentation

6. Results

6.1. Profile of Experimental Group and Control Group

The school selected, was a Co-education school, thus control group and the experimental groups consisted of both boys and girls' students. The classification of sample students based on gender in Phase I Experimentation and Phase II Experimentation are given in the following Table.

Table 2

Profile of Experimental Group and Control Group

Phase	Experimental group Number (Percentage)			Control Group Number (Percentage)		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
Phase I	24 (64.86)	13 (35.14)	37	22 (57.89)	16 (42.10)	38
Phase II	22 (57.89)	16 (42.10)	38	24 (64.86)	13 (35.14)	37

Table shows that 57.89 percent are boys and 42.10 percent are girl students in Phase I of control and Phase II of experimental groups respectively. Further, there are 64.86 percent boys and 35.14 percent girl students in Phase I of Experimental and Phase II of control groups. In both phases, the number of boys is more in the control and experimental group than girls.

6.2. Comparison of the Mean Pre-test scores of Speaking Skills between Experimental and Control Groups.

The dependent variables used for the study are the components as well as overall Speaking Skills in English. The researcher tested the significance of difference in pre-test scores between control group and the experimental group. This was done to test whether the experimental group and the control group are similar in terms of Speaking Skills. The significance of difference between these groups was tested using independent samples t test. The detailed description of analysis is given under the following headings.

The obtained t values in **Phase I** of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(58)} = 3.68, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(57)} = 5.16, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(56)} = 4.15, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(50)} = 5.82, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(57)} = 4.98, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(57)} = 4.46, p < 0.05$) and the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(54)} = 5.14, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level. The obtained t values during **Phase II** of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(53)} = 8.91, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(54)} = 9.06, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(56)} = 8.95, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(50)} = 9.96, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(49)} = 7.51, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(54)} = 8.45, p < 0.05$) and the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(51)} = 9.42, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level.

It is evident that there is a significant difference in the means of the pretest scores of the components of Speaking Skills namely, Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and overall scores on Speaking Skills in English of the students between the Experimental and Control Groups in Phase I and II of the study. The results of the groups differ and show that these groups were not equivalent. The reason is that, the phase I control group was Malayalam medium students and experimental group was English medium students and vice versa during phase II. The English medium students possessed better communication skills in English language.

6.3. Comparison of the Mean Post-test scores of Speaking Skills between Experimental and Control Groups.

The researcher administered the RLAM in the Experimental group and AOM in the Control group. The post-test scores of the Speaking Skills were compared to test whether the scores are significantly different. The independent sample t test was used to test the significance of the differences in mean scores between Experimental and Control Groups. The researcher formulated the following

null hypothesis to test the significance of difference in mean post-test scores of Speaking Skills between Experimental and Control Groups.

There is no significant difference in the Post-test scores of Speaking Skills between Experimental and Control Groups.

The results of the hypothesis test are presented in the following table.

Table 3 :Test of Significance of the Difference in the Mean Post-test scores of Speaking of RLAM and AOM Experimental and Control group

	Components of Speaking Skill	Group	N	Mean	SD	t- test for Equality of Means		
						t-value	df	p-value
Phase I	Task Completion	Experimental	37	1.66	0.59	7.60	59	.000
		Control	38	0.80	0.36			
	Comprehensibility	Experimental	37	1.73	0.64	7.63	61	.000
		Control	38	0.78	0.41			
	Fluency	Experimental	37	1.61	0.61	7.60	60	.000
		Control	38	0.71	0.38			
	Pronunciation	Experimental	37	1.61	0.57	8.68	56	.000
		Control	38	0.68	0.32			
	Vocabulary	Experimental	37	1.53	0.64	6.02	58	.000
Control		38	0.79	0.38				
Language Control	Experimental	37	1.46	0.54	7.11	60	.000	
	Control	38	0.71	0.34				
Speaking Overall	Experimental	37	9.60	3.40	7.96	57	.000	
	Control	38	4.47	1.97				
Phase II	Task Completion	Experimental	38	1.41	0.48	2.05	69	.044
		Control	37	1.66	0.59			
	Comprehensibility	Experimental	38	1.42	0.47	2.37	66	.021
		Control	37	1.73	0.64			
	Fluency	Experimental	38	1.13	0.50	3.73	69	.000
		Control	37	1.62	0.63			
	Pronunciation	Experimental	38	1.12	0.46	4.27	70	.000
		Control	37	1.62	0.56			
	Vocabulary	Experimental	38	1.26	0.40	2.71	57	.009
		Control	37	1.62	0.70			
	Language Control	Experimental	38	1.21	0.41	2.68	62	.009
		Control	37	1.54	0.63			
	Speaking Overall	Experimental	38	7.55	2.45	3.21	64	.002
		Control	37	9.80	3.50			

The obtained *t* values during Phase I of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(59)} = 7.60, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(61)} = 7.63, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(60)} = 7.60, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(56)} = 8.68, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(58)} = 6.02, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(60)} = 7.11, p < 0.05$) and the Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(57)} = 7.96, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level.

The obtained *t* values during Phase II of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(69)} = 2.05, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(66)} = 2.37, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(69)} = 3.73, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(70)} = 4.27, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(57)} = 2.71, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(62)} =$

2.68, $p < 0.05$) and the Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(64)} = 3.21, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level.

It is evident that there is a significant difference in the means of the post-test scores of the components of Speaking Skills namely, Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English of the students between Experimental and Control Groups in Phase I and II of the study.

6.4. Comparison of the Mean Pre-test and Post-test scores of Speaking Skills of Experimental group and Control group.

The comparison of Pre-test scores of Speaking Skills of the experimental group was done to check whether RLAM is effective in improving speaking skills of secondary school students. To test the significance of difference between the Pre-test and Post-test scores, paired sample t test was used.

The following null hypothesis was formulated to test the significance of difference between mean Pre-test and Post-test scores of Speaking Skills of the experimental group.

There is no significant difference between the Pre-test and Post-test scores of Speaking Skills in Experimental group.

Table 4 : Test of Significance of the Difference in the Mean Pre-test and post-test scores of Speaking Skills in Experimental group

	Components of Speaking Skill	Group	N	Mean	SD	t- test for Equality of Means		
						t-value	df	p-value
Phase I	Task Completion	Pre - test	37	1.05	0.51	10.39	36	.000
		Post - test	37	1.66	0.59			
	Comprehensibility	Pre - test	37	1.22	0.57	9.69	36	.000
		Post - test	37	1.73	0.64			
	Fluency	Pre - test	37	1.05	0.61	10.98	36	.000
		Post - test	37	1.61	0.61			
	Pronunciation	Pre - test	37	1.18	0.56	9.82	36	.000
		Post - test	37	1.61	0.57			
	Vocabulary	Pre - test	37	1.14	0.51	8.17	36	.000
Post - test		37	1.53	0.64				
Language Control	Pre - test	37	1.03	0.50	8.99	36	.000	
	Post - test	37	1.46	0.54				
Speaking Overall	Pre - test	37	6.66	3.04	13.32	36	.000	
	Post - test	37	9.60	3.40				
Phase II	Task Completion	Pre - test	38	0.80	0.36	12.83	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.41	0.48			
	Comprehensibility	Pre - test	38	0.78	0.41	14.55	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.42	0.47			
	Fluency	Pre - test	38	0.71	0.38	9.89	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.13	0.50			
	Pronunciation	Pre - test	38	0.68	0.32	8.85	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.12	0.46			
	Vocabulary	Pre - test	38	0.79	0.38	14.13	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.26	0.40			
	Language Control	Pre - test	38	0.71	0.34	12.93	37	.000
		Post - test	38	1.21	0.41			
	Speaking Overall	Pre - test	38	4.47	1.97	15.23	37	.000
		Post - test	38	7.55	2.45			

The obtained t values in Phase I for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(36)} = 10.39, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(36)} = 9.69, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(36)} = 10.98, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(36)} = 9.82, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(36)} = 8.17, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(36)} = 8.99, p < 0.05$) and the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(36)} = 13.32, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level. The obtained t values in Phase II for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(37)} = 12.83, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(37)} = 14.55, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(37)} = 9.89, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(37)} = 8.85, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(37)} = 14.13, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(37)} = 12.93, p < 0.05$) and the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(37)} = 15.23, p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level.

It is evident that there is significant difference between the means of the pre-test and post-test scores of the components of Speaking Skills namely, Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and Speaking overall of the students in the Experimental group in Phase I and II of the study.

6.5. Comparison of the Mean Pre-test and post-test scores of Speaking Skills of Control group

The comparison of pre-test scores of Speaking Skills of the control group is important as RLAM was not administered in the control group. This comparison was also used to find out whether the existing method is effective in improving Speaking Skills of secondary school students. To test the significance of difference between the Pre-test and Post-test scores, paired sample t test was used.

The following null hypothesis was formulated to test the significance of difference between mean pre and post-test scores of Speaking Skill of the control groups.

There is no significant difference between the Pre-test and Post-test scores of Speaking Skill of Control group.

Table 5 : Data and Results of Test of Significance of the Difference in the Mean Pre-test and Post-test scores of Speaking Skills in Control group

	Components of Speaking Skill	Group	N	Mean	SD	t- test for Equality of Means		
						t-value	df	p-value
Phase I	Task Completion	Pre - test	38	0.70	0.30	1.67	37	.103
		Post - test	38	0.75	0.38			
	Comprehensibility	Pre - test	38	0.66	0.33	1.96	37	.058
		Post - test	38	0.72	0.40			
	Fluency	Pre - test	38	0.58	0.34	1.83	37	.076
		Post - test	38	0.65	0.43			
	Pronunciation	Pre - test	38	0.59	0.26	1.78	37	.083
		Post - test	38	0.63	0.30			
Vocabulary	Pre - test	38	0.66	0.29	1.78	37	.083	
	Post - test	38	0.70	0.32				
Language Control	Pre - test	38	0.61	0.29	1.96	37	.058	
	Post - test	38	0.67	0.35				
Speaking Overall	Pre - test	38	3.79	1.61	4.27	37	.000	
	Post - test	38	4.12	1.70				
Phase II	Task Completion	Pre - test	37	1.66	0.59	1.78	36	.083
		Post - test	37	1.70	0.56			
	Comprehensibility	Pre - test	37	1.73	0.64	1.78	36	.083
		Post - test	37	1.77	0.65			
	Fluency	Pre - test	37	1.61	0.61	1.78	36	.083
		Post - test	37	1.65	0.62			

	Pronunciation	Pre - test	37	1.61	0.57	1.27	36	.212
		Post - test	37	1.73	0.78			
	Vocabulary	Pre - test	37	1.53	0.64	1.78	36	.083
		Post - test	37	1.57	0.65			
	Language Control	Pre - test	37	1.46	0.54	1.43	36	.160
		Post - test	37	1.49	0.53			
	Speaking Overall	Pre - test	37	9.60	3.40	2.70	36	.011
		Post - test	37	9.91	3.38			

The obtained t values in Phase I of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(37)} = 1.67, p > 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(37)} = 1.96, p > 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(37)} = 1.83, p > 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(37)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(37)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(37)} = 1.96, p > 0.05$) are not significant at 0.05 level except the Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(37)} = 4.27, p < 0.05$). The obtained t values in Phase II of the study for Speaking Skills are Task Completion ($t_{(36)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(36)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(36)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(36)} = 1.27, p > 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(36)} = 1.78, p > 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(36)} = 1.43, p > 0.05$) are not significant at 0.05 level except the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(36)} = 2.70, p < 0.05$).

It is evident that there is no significant difference between the means of the Pre-test and Post-test scores of the components of Speaking Skills namely, Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary and Language Control of the students in the control group in Phase I and II of the study.

6.6. Comparison of the mean Gain Scores of Speaking Skills between Experimental and Control Groups

In order to find out the effectiveness of the RLAM over AOM of instruction on speaking skills in English among the secondary school students, the researcher analysed gain scores of the students in the experimental and control groups. The gain scores of overall Speaking Skill, various Speaking Skill components of the students in the experimental and control group were computed by subtracting pre-test scores from post-test scores. The researcher tested the significance of difference in gain scores between the control group and the experimental group by applying independent sample t test. The following null hypothesis has been formulated to test the significance of difference in mean gain scores of Speaking Skill between the Experimental and Control Groups.

There is no significant difference in the Gain Scores of the Speaking Skill between Experimental and Control Groups.

Table 6 : Test of Significance of the Difference in the mean Gain scores of Speaking Skill between Experimental and Control Groups

	Components of Speaking Skill	Group	N	Mean	SD	t- test for Equality of Means		
						t-value	df	p-value
Phase I	Task Completion	Experimental	37	0.61	0.36	7.4	73	.000
		Control	38	0.11	0.21			
	Comprehensibility	Experimental	37	0.51	0.32	5.97	73	.000
		Control	38	0.12	0.25			
	Fluency	Control	38	0.13	0.22	6.80	73	.000
		Experimental	37	0.55	0.31			
	Pronunciation	Experimental	37	0.43	0.27	5.92	73	.001
		Control	38	0.09	0.23			
	Vocabulary	Experimental	37	0.39	0.30	4.13	73	.000
		Control	38	0.13	0.25			

	Language Control	Experimental	37	0.43	0.29	5.58	73	.000
		Control	38	0.11	0.21			
	Speaking Overall	Experimental	37	2.93	1.34	8.14	73	.000
		Control	38	0.68	1.03			
Phase II	Task Completion	Experimental	38	0.71	0.34	11.19	73	.000
		Control	37	0.04	0.14			
	Comprehensibility	Experimental	38	0.76	0.32	12.64	73	.000
		Control	37	0.04	0.14			
	Fluency	Experimental	38	0.55	0.34	8.48	73	.000
		Control	37	0.04	0.14			
	Pronunciation	Experimental	38	0.53	0.37	3.61	73	.001
		Control	37	0.12	0.58			
	Vocabulary	Experimental	38	0.61	0.26	11.65	73	.000
		Control	37	0.04	0.14			
	Language Control	Experimental	38	0.61	0.29	11.46	73	.000
		Control	37	0.03	0.11			
	Speaking Overall	Experimental	38	3.76	1.52	12.66	73	.000
		Control	37	0.31	0.70			

From the table, it is that the means of gain scores of the students in the experimental group is more than that of the control group for all the components of Speaking Skills namely Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and Overall Speaking Skills in English.

The obtained t values in Phase I of the study for the components, Task Completion ($t_{(73)} = 7.4$, $p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(73)} = 5.97$, $p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(73)} = 6.80$, $p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(73)} = 5.92$, $p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(73)} = 4.13$, $p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(73)} = 5.58$, $p < 0.05$) and Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(73)} = 8.14$, $p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level. The obtained t values in Phase II of the study for the components, Task Completion ($t_{(73)} = 11.19$, $p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(73)} = 12.64$, $p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(73)} = 8.48$, $p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($t_{(73)} = 3.61$, $p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(73)} = 11.65$, $p < 0.05$), Language Control ($t_{(73)} = 11.46$, $p < 0.05$) and Overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(73)} = 12.66$, $p < 0.05$) are significant at 0.05 level.

From this, it is clear that there is significant difference between the means of gain scores on all the components of Speaking Skills namely Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and Overall Speaking Skills in English of the students in the experimental and control groups. From the results it is evident that the students exposed to RLAM achieved significantly higher scores on Speaking Skills in English when compared with AOM. RLAM is found to be more effective than AOM in improving Speaking Skills in English among the students of Standard IX.

6.7. Effect of RLAM on Speaking Skills of the Experimental and Control Groups using Analysis of Covariance

In order to find out the effect of RLAM over the existing AOM of instruction on Speaking Skills in English among the secondary school students, the researcher analysed gain scores of the students in the experimental and control groups using Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

In order to analyse the effect of RLAM over AOM on Speaking Skills in English, the researcher formulated the null hypothesis.

There is no significant effect of RLAM over AOM on Speaking Skills in English among secondary school students.

The null hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA.

Phase I Experimentation

Table 7 presents the results of ANCOVA.

Table 7

Summary of ANCOVA of Pre-test and Post-test scores in Experimental and Control Groups

Phase I	Components of Speaking Skill	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F-value	p-value
	Task Completion	Pre-test		1	11.20	11.20	132.11
RLAM			1	4.33	4.33	51.14	.000
Error			72	6.10	0.09		
Corrected Total			74	31.14			
Comprehensibility	Pre-test		1	15.19	15.19	183.72	.000
	RLAM		1	2.26	2.26	27.34	.000
	Error		72	5.95	0.08		
	Corrected Total		74	38.19			
Fluency	Pre-test		1	13.88	13.88	199.55	.000
	RLAM		1	3.43	3.43	49.35	.000
	Error		72	5.01	0.07		
	Corrected Total		74	33.99			
Pronunciation	Pre-test		1	10.91	10.91	179.87	.000
	RLAM		1	2.04	2.04	33.59	.000
	Error		72	4.37	0.06		
	Corrected Total		74	31.28			
Vocabulary	Pre-test		1	15.01	15.01	204.50	.000
	RLAM		1	0.63	0.63	8.54	.005
	Error		72	5.28	0.07		
	Corrected Total		74	30.49			
Language Control	Pre-test		1	10.41	10.41	162.88	.000
	RLAM		1	1.87	1.87	29.30	.000
	Error		72	4.60	0.064		
	Corrected Total		74	25.52			
Speaking Overall	Pre-test		1	456.05	456.05	317.74	.000
	RLAM		1	63.94	63.94	44.55	.000
	Error		72	103.34	1.44		
	Corrected Total		74	1051.00			

ANCOVA results signify that, after adjusting pre-test scores, there is significant difference between the experimental and control groups in their Speaking Skills in English based on the objective of attaining the components of Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control, Speaking Overall.

Task Completion ($F_{(1,72)} = 51.14, p < 0.05$) Comprehensibility ($F_{(1,72)}=27.34, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($F_{(1,72)}=49.35, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($F_{(1,72)}=33.59, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($F_{(1,72)}=8.54, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($F_{(1,72)} = 29.30, p < 0.05$) and Speaking Overall ($F_{(1,72)} = 44.55, p < 0.05$).

The *F* values are found to be significant at 0.05 level and so the null hypothesis that ‘there is no significant effect of the RLAM over the AOM on Speaking Skills in English of the students’ of Standard IX is rejected. Both the observed and adjusted means show that students taught through RLAM of Instruction achieved better when compared to the students taught through AOM of teaching English. It is implied that RLAM instruction is better than AOM of teaching English for enhancing Speaking Skills in English based on the Speaking Skills among secondary school students.

Phase II Experimentation

The following table presents the results regarding the analysis of phase II Experimentation.

Table 8

Summary of ANCOVA of Pre-test and Post-test scores in Experimental and Control groups

Phase II	Components of Speaking Skill	Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F-value	p-value
	Task Completion	Pre-test		1	14.67	14.67	211.96
RLAM			1	3.59	3.59	51.89	.000
Error			72	4.98	0.07		
Corrected Total			74	21.29			
Comprehensibility	Pre-test		1	19.00	19.00	300.28	.000
	RLAM		1	4.62	4.62	73.06	.000
	Error		72	4.56	0.06		
	Corrected Total		74	25.49			
Fluency	Pre-test		1	18.19	18.19	257.74	.000
	RLAM		1	2.42	2.42	34.30	.000
	Error		72	5.08	0.07		
	Corrected Total		74	28.29			
Pronunciation	Pre-test		1	12.39	12.39	52.07	.000
	RLAM		1	0.93	0.93	3.93	.050
	Error		72	17.13	0.24		
	Corrected Total		74	36.52			
Vocabulary	Pre-test		1	17.68	17.68	389.77	.000
	RLAM		1	3.25	3.25	71.65	.000
	Error		72	3.27	0.05		
	Corrected Total		74	22.69			
Language Control	Pre-test		1	13.02	13.02	264.66	.000
	RLAM		1	2.89	2.89	58.81	.000
	Error		72	3.54	0.05		
	Corrected Total		74	17.99			
Speaking Overall	Pre-test		1	531.99	531.99	370.70	.000
	RLAM		1	106.92	106.92	74.50	.000
	Error		72	103.33	1.44		
	Corrected Total		74	739.09			

After performing ANCOVA and the results signify that, after adjusting pre-test scores, there is significant difference between the experimental and control groups in their Speaking Skills in English based on the objective of attaining the components of Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control, Speaking Overall.

Task Completion ($F_{(1,72)} = 51.89, p < 0.05$), Comprehensibility ($F_{(1,72)} = 73.06, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($F_{(1,72)} = 34.30, p < 0.05$), Pronunciation ($F_{(1,72)} = 3.93, p < 0.05$), Vocabulary ($F_{(1,72)} = 71.65, p < 0.05$), Language Control ($F_{(1,72)} = 58.81, p < 0.05$) and Speaking Overall ($F_{(1,72)} = 74.50, p < 0.05$). The *F* values are found to be significant at 0.05 level and so the null hypothesis that ‘there is no

significant effect of the RLAM over AOM on Speaking Skills in English of the students' of Standard IX is rejected. Both the observed and adjusted means show that students taught through the RLAM of Instruction is found to be more effective than when compared to the students taught through AOM of teaching English. It is implied that RLAM instruction is better than AOM of teaching English for enhancing Speaking Skills in English based on the Speaking Skills among secondary school students.

7. Discussion of Findings

The study analysed the effectiveness of the RLAM on the Speaking skills in English among the students of Standard IX when compared with AOM. The researcher compared the pre-test scores of both the experimental groups by using the test of significance between the groups and found that the RLAM is effective in improving the components of Speaking Skills namely Task completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Coherence and Cohesion, Pronunciation, Vocabulary and Language control. Therefore, the investigator compared the effects of RLAM on the components.

The investigator compared the effect of the RLAM on the dependent variables over AOM in many ways.

- Comparison of the post-test scores of the experimental and control groups using the test of significance of difference between the means of two independent groups
- Comparison of the gain scores on the dependent variables of the experimental and control groups using the test of significance of difference between the two independent groups.
- Testing the effect of RLAM on the dependent variables by controlling the pre-test scores on the dependent variables using ANCOVA.

In all the results of the tests, the investigator found that RLAM was effective in improving Speaking Skills in English. Variable wise as well as sub component wise analysis, the investigator found that the effect of RLAM was superior to existing AOM except the component vocabulary. Thus, it means that, RLAM was effective in improving the components of Speaking Skills. The findings of the present study agree with the findings of [Netto \(2008\)](#) Mathai (2010) who found reflective thinking strategy was more effective than the conventional method of instructions. The findings of Netto (2008) on Reflective thinking strategy of teaching are in accordance with that, it is more effective than conventional method of direct instruction for the achievement of cognitive variables among secondary school students. Reflective thinking strategy of teaching is equally effective on the performance of secondary school students with high, average and low levels of creativity. Reflective thinking strategy of teaching is more effective than conventional method of direct instruction for the achievement of affective variables among secondary school students.

The findings of the study are in agreement with the findings of Mathai (2010) who found that reflective practices could activate lexico-semantic information, break down the comprehension or production process according to the structural levels of analysis, integrate information between sentences in a discourse, and build a sort of computational architecture that can be used to represent information coherently. Journal writing, and reflective discussions for developing communicative competence of learner's reflective practices could build a language structure capable of incorporating the syntactic, semantic and linguistic features of language and could thereby promote effective communication. On the basis of the findings of the study, it can be emphatically stated that reflection can be taught although it does require much energy from the teacher.

The results of the study found some similarities with that of [Lepcha \(2013\)](#). Reflective practices particularly teaching helps the teachers to gain better self-awareness about their practices in professional development. Overall, the findings of the study revealed that intervention on reflection enabled teachers to involve in reflection in a more productive way by keeping a diary of their teaching, finding core problems in language teaching and the method to solve them collaboratively with colleagues. More importantly, teachers learnt to reflect consciously not only to assess their teaching after the class but also to reflect during the class about the aptness of techniques and methods being employed in a class.

The observations of ([Osterman & Kottkamp, 1993](#)) say that Traditional Model and Reflective Practice Model are the contrasting approaches to professional development. In reflective

practice model the researcher becomes a Practitioner as action researcher. The study found that the boys and girls taught in RLAM do not significantly differ in their respective performance with respect to their Speaking Skills in English. In other words, gender does not influence on the performance of the students who were exposed to RLAM. This finding is substantiated by the studies of [Mathai \(2010\)](#). The present study convincingly revealed that the Reflective Language Acquisition Model is more effective in nurturing Speaking Skills in English among the secondary school students of Kerala State. The study confirms that, it is worthy of incorporating reflective practices in enriching language learning situations. Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that the Reflective Language Acquisition Model should be a part of our language education classrooms. The researcher would be sufficiently rewarded, if the findings of the study are utilised in teaching English by the teachers of English. The investigator hopes that this study will make language learning easy and meaningful for the speedy acquisition of fundamental language skills. It is anticipated that more extensive research would further be conducted in the area of reflective pedagogy.

8. Limitations and Future Research Directions

The present study was carried out in order to find out the effectiveness of Reflective Language Acquisition Model on the speaking skills in English among the Secondary School Students. Future research studies related to reflective practices can be conducted in other subjects like mathematics, social sciences at primary, higher secondary and tertiary levels and similar studies can be done in different syllabi namely CBSE, ICSE, and IGCSE. Further, studies can be conducted to compare the effect of other language models or approaches being used in language education. Future researches can be carried out to test the differences in acquiring speaking skills using RLAM, among the students of rural, urban, tribal and coastal regions. Similar studies can be carried out for longer durations in different experimental designs and with larger samples comprising students from different districts can be carried out.

In order to assess language skills, after applying RLAM, instead of rubrics, band descriptors of IELTS can be followed for public schools. Further, linguistic intelligence can be tested among the students, before the implementation of the model in order to identify the level of progress in their acquisition of language skills with respect to intelligence. A survey can be carried out among the students along with the application of the model, in order to get more information about the student perspective. Teacher efficacy also can be tested among a few teachers of English and can be tested the effect of the model among their application of RLAM.

The limitations of the present study also promise fruitful avenues for future research. First, the study was restricted to English language learning. The test focused on assessing the Speaking Skill of the learners of secondary school students. Second, the sample was selected only from Kottayam district. Third, language skill is a qualitative measure, converting that into a quantitative measure may not be the equivalent assessment criteria.

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